

Supplementary Material: Patterns and Enablers for Frugal Innovation in Small Industries in Resource-Constrained Environments

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Table S1 contains the 40 articles in the final corpus used for analysis in the RSL.

TABLE S1. LIST OF THE ARTICLES IN THE FINAL CORPUS (N = 40).

Authors	Title	Journal	Year	DOI
Tiwari & Herstatt (2012)	Assessing India's lead market potential for cost-effective innovations	Journal of Indian Business Research	2012	10.1108/17554191211228029
Lim <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Capability building through innovation for unserved lower end mega markets	Technovation	2013	10.1016/j.technovation.2013.06.010
Alamelu <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Preference of E-bike by women in India -a niche market for auto manufacturers	Business: Theory and Practice	2015	10.3846/btp.2015.431
Winterhalter <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Business Models for Frugal Innovation in Emerging Markets: The Case of the Medical Device and Laboratory Equipment Industry	Technovation	2017	10.1016/j.technovation.2017.07.002
Agarwal <i>et al.</i> (2017)	A systematic literature review of constraint-based innovations: State of the art and future perspectives	IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management	2017	10.1109/TEM.2016.2620562
Dellermann (2017)	Going East: a framework for reverse innovation in SMEs	Journal of Business Strategy	2017	10.1108/JBS-02-2016-0014
Kuo (2017)	Harnessing frugal innovation to foster clean technologies	Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy	2017	10.1007/s10098-016-1304-y
Mazieri <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Frugal innovation beyond emerging countries: the key role of developed countries	Revista Gestão & Tecnologia -Journal of Management And Technology	2017	10.20397/2177-6652/2017.v17i4.1280
Mourtzis (2018)	Design of customised products and manufacturing networks: towards frugal innovation	International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing	2018	10.1080/0951192X.2018.1509131
Thun (2018)	Innovation at the middle of the pyramid: State policy, market segmentation, and the Chinese automotive sector	Technovation	2018	10.1016/j.technovation.2018.02.007
Wang <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Product innovation in emerging economies: product architecture and organisational capabilities in Geely and Tata	International Journal of Automotive Technology and Management	2018	10.1504/IJATM.2018.097348
Devi & Kumar (2018)	Frugal Innovations and Actor-Network Theory: A Case of	European Journal of Development Research	2018	10.1057/s41287-017-0116-1

	Bamboo Shoots Processing in Manipur, India			
Hyypiä and Khan (2018)	Overcoming Barriers to Frugal Innovation: Emerging Opportunities for Finnish SMEs in Brazilian Market	Technology Innovation Management Review	2018	10.22215/timreview/1151
Wei <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Towards an asymmetry-based view of Chinese firms' technological catch-up	Frontiers Of Business Research In China	2018	10.1186/s11782-018-0041-y
Lim and Fujimoto (2019)	Frugal innovation and design changes expanding the cost-performance frontier: A Schumpeterian approach	Research Policy	2019	10.1016/j.respol.2018.10.014
Krishnan and Prashantham (2019)	Innovation in and from India: The who, where, what, and when	Global Strategy Journa	2019	10.1002/gsj.1207
Lu <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Deprecated in policy, abundant in market? The frugal innovation of Chinese low-speed EV industry	International Journal of Production Economics	2020	10.1016/j.ijpe.2019.107583
Niroumand <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Frugal innovation enablers: a comprehensive framework	International Journal of Innovation Science	2020	10.1108/IJIS-10-2019-0099
von Janda <i>et al.</i> (2020)	What frugal products are and why they matter: A cross-national multi-method study	Journal of Cleaner Production	2020	10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118977
Kronemeyer <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Finding frugal patent candidates: testing a thesaurus-based process model in the field of small household appliances	International Journal of Innovation Science	2020	10.1108/IJIS-04-2020-0052
Gerybadze and Klein (2020)	Frugal innovation strategies and global competition in wind power	International Journal of Technology Management	2020	10.1504/IJTM.2020.109241
Mergaliyeva (2020)	The nature of innovation ecosystem of the western kazakh state university	International Journal of Higher Education	2020	10.5430/IJHE.V9N4P254
Lim <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Frugal innovation and leapfrogging innovation approach to the Industry 4.0 challenge for a developing country	Asian Journal of Technology Innovation	2020	10.1080/19761597.2020.1786707
Borchardt <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Leveraging frugal innovation in micro- and small enterprises at the base of the pyramid in Brazil: an analysis through the lens of dynamic capabilities	Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies	2021	10.1108/JEEE-02-2020-0031
Corsini <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Frugal innovation in a crisis: the digital fabrication maker response to COVID-19	R&D Management	2021	10.1111/radm.12446
Jayabalan <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Reshaping higher educational institutions through frugal open innovation	Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity	2021	10.3390/joitmc7020145
Niroumand <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Frugal innovation enablers, critical success factors and barriers: A systematic review	Creativity and Innovation Management	2021	10.1111/caim.12436
Agarwal <i>et al.</i> (2021).	Constraint-Based Thinking: A Structured Approach for Developing Frugal Innovations	IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management	2021	10.1109/TEM.2020.3042929

Walden and Lie (2021)	University-Industry Collaboration in Frugal Innovation through Prototyping: The Case of a Firefighter Cooling Vest	IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management	2021	10.1109/TEM.2020.3032198
D'Angelo and Magnusson (2021)	A Bibliometric Map of Intellectual Communities in Frugal Innovation Literature	IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management	2021	10.1109/TEM.2020.2994043
Fischer <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Knowledge transfer for frugal innovation: where do entrepreneurial universities stand?	Journal of Knowledge Management	2021	10.1108/JKM-01-2020-0040
Vaska <i>et al.</i> (2021)	The Digital Transformation of Business Model Innovation: A Structured Literature Review	Frontiers in Psychology	2021	10.3389/fpsyg.2020.539363
Lange <i>et al.</i> (2023)	How frugal innovation and inclusive business are linked to tackle low-income markets	Journal of Small Business Management	2021	10.1080/00472778.2021.1924380
Adjimah <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Examining the Role of Regulation in the Commercialisation of Indigenous Innovation in Sub-Saharan African Economies: Evidence from the Ghanaian Small-Scale Industry	Administrative Sciences	2022	10.3390/admsci12030118
Montoya and Cervantes (2022)	The Role of Regulation in the Development and Internationalization of Social Firms	Sustainability (Switzerland)	2022	10.3390/su14127047
Borchardt <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Germinating seeds in dry soil: examining the process of frugal innovation in micro- and small-enterprises at the base of the pyramid	European Business Review	2022	10.1108/EBR-12-2020-0325
Iqbal <i>et al.</i> (2022)	To walk in beauty: Sustainable leadership, frugal innovation and environmental performance	Managerial and Decision Economics	2022	10.1002/mde.3415
D'Angelo and Magnusson (2022)	Frugal Approaches to Innovation: Industrial Settings and Innovation Strategies	IEEE Engineering Management Review	2022	10.1109/EMR.2022.3171133
Kwan <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Digital taxation to promote frugal innovation in institutions of higher learning: A three-decade systematic literature review	F1000Research	2022	10.12688/f1000research.73318.2
Xuecheng and Iqbal (2022)	Managerial Networking and Frugal Innovation: Situational Leadership Perspective	Frontiers in Psychology	2022	10.3389/fpsyg.2022.948530

Tables S2, S3, and S4 present syntheses of the articles within each of the clusters identified in the bibliographic coupling analysis.

TABLE S2. CLUSTER 1 ARTICLES, WITH THEIR SYNTHESIS.

Author	Objective	Method	Results/Contributions
Tiwari and Herstatt (2012)	Identify the factors impacting India's emerging role as a source of frugal innovations.	Case study	The case studies show that products developed in India have a high chance of global diffusion in similar developing countries and industrialized nations. India's large volumes, dynamic markets, cost advantage, technical capabilities, and global linkages make it a market leader. Domestic and multinational companies should use India as a testbed for frugal and disruptive innovations, anticipating emerging needs.
Lim <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Investigate Tata Motors' Nano as an exploratory case of building innovation capabilities.	Case study	A case study on product innovation in a large developing country sheds light on building innovation capacity. By creating an original product for the Underend Lower Mega market (ULM) and achieving radical cost reduction, this study opens a discussion on innovation capacity. The ULM innovation, unprecedented in the automobile industry, generated competition among global companies—a rarity for developing countries or newly industrialized economies.
Agarwal <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Develop an SLR on constraint-based innovation approaches to investigate the progress of existing research and use the insights to define future research paths.	SLR	Research increasingly focuses on “bottom-up” and structured innovation, reducing dependence on technology transfers from the West. Although understanding the bottom segment of the pyramid and product conceptualization has been emphasized, other aspects of the innovation process – such as development, diffusion, and technological influence – remain gaps.
Kuo (2017)	Investigate how various organizations leverage frugal innovation to develop affordable, clean technologies or green products.	Case study	The case organizations effectively addressed underserved consumers' neglected needs and environmental concerns. They leveraged readily available resources, prioritized simplicity in product design, and considered accessibility requirements. Their experience highlights the potential for clean technology developers to create affordable, sustainable products. Incorporating frugal innovation into green product design can enhance product success and reduce reliance on government subsidies, promoting sustainability.
Dellermann (2017)	Provide a framework for how Western small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) can drive reverse innovation success.	Case study	SMEs can benefit from reverse innovation in emerging markets, even if they have not previously engaged in exports or direct operations in developing countries.
Winterhalter <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Investigate how companies can design and establish business models for emerging markets.	Case study	Results indicated that an affordable customer value proposition generates significant value in resource-constrained environments. Business models serve target

			customers and enhance the entire healthcare system in their respective markets. Companies achieve this value through rigorous innovation and primarily capture it via product sales, complemented by valuable marketing effects.
Wei <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Propose a two-stage model of technological recovery of Chinese companies and provide explanations based on asymmetry.	Document analysis	A two-stage model for Chinese companies' technological catch-up was proposed. Initially, these companies focus on knowledge accumulation through frugal innovation to capture low-cost markets. Later, they prioritize knowledge creation via radical innovation to target the high-end market. These companies also leverage technology spillovers, university research, and local cluster knowledge. Bricolage of resources plays a crucial role in their frugal innovation.
Devi and Kumar (2018)	Explore the process of frugal innovations in the informal bamboo shoot food processing sector in the Indian state of Manipur using Actor-Network Theory.	Case study/Ethnographic study	Frugal innovations emerge from negotiations among various actors, aiming to expand networks and navigate complex relationships during the translation process. The principles of Actor-Network Theory (ANT), emphasizing symmetry and the involvement of nonhuman actors, enhance our understanding of frugal innovation, particularly in the informal sector.
Hyypiä and Khan (2018)	Test existing online learning services from Finnish companies and obtain authentic feedback from users (students and teachers) in Brazil, thus enabling simplified service development.	Case study	This study emphasized the importance of frugal innovation in SMEs' bottom-up development processes. Finnish SMEs can succeed by providing comprehensive solutions based on real user needs rather than merely offering products and services. Integrating these solutions into Brazilian partner operations is critical. Incorporating frugal innovation from the outset is crucial for Finnish SMEs.
Thun (2018)	Investigate how different market segments within an industrial sector play a unique role in the development process and how the absence of any segment can inhibit the upward trajectory of emerging market companies.	Case study	China adapted traditional industrial policy tools in synthesis, including high tariffs and technology transfer controls. However, these policies focused on learning from global operators, limiting the lower market segment. Domestic companies adapted to foreign partners' weaknesses (high costs, products for developed markets) but lacked independent design skills. Paradoxically, state policies promoting competitiveness abroad hindered leveraging natural advantages in the domestic market.
Lim and Fujimoto (2019)	Clarify and expand the concept of frugal innovation, developing a framework that links theories of innovation, and the phenomenon called frugal innovation.	Case study	Summarily, frugal innovation can enhance product performance under extreme budget constraints. Integral architecture plays a crucial role, in challenging assumptions about low-cost/sufficiently good simple products. Integrative and strategic approaches are essential for enabling frugal innovations across various functions within companies and industries.

Krishnan and Prashantham (2019)	Provide an overview of the drivers and distinctive features of innovation in India that, on the one hand, represent great potential but, on the other, appear to be limited.	Case study	Indian organizations have contributed to process, incremental, and frugal innovations, creating value for businesses and consumers. However, much of this innovation has been within the technological frontier, focused on cost reduction for Indian consumers. Foreign multinationals also play a role in patent-creating R&D, especially for global products. Spillovers from these entities have fueled the emergence of startups, some of which pursue product and frugal innovation.
Lu <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Exploring a new deprecated policy context rather than traditional institution voids, constructing a frugal innovation framework from the BE perspective by focusing on focal firms, and proposing three frugal innovation patterns under different resource constraints	Case study	This paper contributed to frugal innovation research by exploring a new policy context beyond traditional institutional voids. It constructs a frugal innovation framework from the business ecosystem perspective, focusing on focal firms and proposing three patterns of frugal innovation under varying resource constraints.
Lim <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Develop a framework for solving the problems in responding to the Industry 4.0 challenge in Thailand, having frugal innovation and leapfrogging innovation concepts as theoretical bases.	Case study	This paper provided a framework to address two key challenges: the investment dilemma due to low affordability markets and firms' limited capabilities and the fragmented stakeholder problem. It also connects frugal innovation and leapfrogging discussions to the Industry 4.0 challenge.
Jayabalan <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Investigate private universities' challenges from the practitioners' perspective and offer a practical solution. The study also attempts to identify whether private universities need changes to the business model or operations required by private universities to sustain their competitive advantage in the current environment.	SLR	The study highlights how private higher educational institutions (PHEIs) can leverage intangible assets for frugal open innovation. By focusing on core functions, integrating with industry and communities, and enhancing operational efficiency, PHEIs can achieve impactful results.
Vaska <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Analyze the development of the field of digital transformation and understand the impact of digital technologies on business model innovation (BMI) through a structured literature review.	SLR	Digital transformation has significantly impacted value creation, delivery, and capture across various sectors. Companies now cocreate value with customers through personalized manufacturing, adopt servitization strategies, expand product portfolios, and leverage digital platforms and ecosystems. Additionally, digital transformation enables addressing sustainability challenges and meeting specific customer needs. Companies must assess their competencies, functions, and capabilities in response to these changes.

TABLE S3. CLUSTER 2 ARTICLES, WITH THEIR SYNTHESIS.

Author	Objective	Method	Results/Contributions
Mourtzis (2018)	Present a unified framework of an augmented reality product customization application that supports realistic product visualization to extract end-user requirements that provide information to a web-based supplier selection and network design tool that considers frugal criteria.	Case study	The proposed framework integrates customer opinions into production processes by aligning unique solutions with requirements and incorporating them into a frugal supplier network design. The AR product design tool allows customer involvement during new product development or existing product redesign, ensuring market needs are met. Customers actively contribute to the manufacturing network by influencing its design through their configurations.
von Janda <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Develop a comprehensive conceptualization and operationalization of product frugality.	SLR and Factorial Exploratory Analysis	The study identified product frugality as a formative construct with four key dimensions: consumption cost, sustainability, simplicity, and basic quality. Notably, the findings emphasize that low cost and environmental sustainability should be integrated rather than pitted against each other to achieve genuinely frugal products. Overall, this research contributes to a shared understanding of product frugality, acknowledging its multidimensional nature.
Niroumand <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Propose a framework for the dimensions of frugal innovation enablers in SMEs.	Case study	The study found that key enablers of frugal innovation include world-class design, human factors, marketing, support, knowledge, social aspects, prototyping, cultural considerations, environmental factors, distinctive brand creation, core function focus, local R&D, business model cost reduction, and low-cost production.
Gerybadze and Klein (2020)	Analyze the interaction between product innovation and process innovation in wind energy and how this leads to greater efficiency in generation and consumption of energy.	Case study	As a prototype, the study showed that the wind energy industry demonstrates an evolutionary perspective for improving and globally disseminating renewable energy technologies. Key factors include learning curves, cost reductions, and industry consolidation. Frugal innovation will play a crucial role in creating new global expansion opportunities. Notably, emerging countries already account for 54% of new global wind energy investments, a trend likely to continue due to frugal design concepts and efficiency improvements.
Mergaliyeva (2020)	Reveal how to implement high innovation and creativity approaches at Western Kazakhstan State University (WKSU). The study explored factors influencing the development of an innovative culture in universities and industry.	Analysis of the PESTLE structure, the Innovation Value Chain (IVC) model, and the Corporate Entrepreneurship Assessment Instrument (CEAI)	The findings indicate that WKSU would benefit from frugal innovation, which presents a fresh entrepreneurial opportunity for companies in low-income countries with limited resources. Opting for frugal innovation creates a new business scenario and contributes to sustainability.
Fischer <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Analyze an entrepreneurial university's strategic knowledge transfer	Case study	The study emphasized the multidimensional dynamics of frugal innovations resulting from university-

	practices to foster frugal innovations in an emerging economy.		industry collaborations. Key dimensions include universities' internal capabilities to promote frugal innovations and connect with markets and the surrounding innovation ecosystems. Additionally, the overarching institutional structure plays a crucial role.
Walden and Lie (2021)	Demonstrate an alignment of practices and values inherent in university-industry collaboration (UIC) projects with those evident in frugal innovation design.	Case study	The study found a complementary connection between frugal innovation UIC projects for manufacturing SMEs. Despite resource constraints, SMEs are encouraged to innovate with support from university research units. Design teams working on these projects must adopt a frugal approach to reduce risks associated with product production. This overarching determination is evident from the research literature alone.
Niroumand <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Develop a model for the enablers, critical success factors (CSFs), and barriers to frugal innovation.	SLR and Maxqda10 (software)	The study found that frugal innovation benefits from optimizing energy consumption, collaborating with local companies, receiving management support, addressing local market needs, and reducing profit margins. However, barriers to FI include a lack of business vision among regional partners, senior management reluctance, R&D challenges, prototyping difficulties in product development, and currency fluctuations.
Agarwal <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Investigate how a constraints-based approach can be applied to the frugal product development process.	Theoretical sampling/Root cause analysis (RCA)	The constraints-based thinking approach involves identifying existing constraints, conducting root cause analysis, mapping causes to product characteristics, and developing a minimally viable product or prototype. Emphasizing sustainability, such as adopting cradle-to-cradle approaches, can address the urgent need to promote sustainability across various levels.
D'Angelo and Magnusson (2021)	Examine the intellectual structure of the developing domain of frugal innovation research to identify the most active and influential communities, the most seminal works, and the most active scholars.	Bibliometric analysis	This article assesses the current state of frugal innovation. While it doesn't delve into detailed discussions or synthesize previous research, our findings are relevant for academics interested in advancing FI research. The bibliometric review was an auxiliary tool to identify existing theoretical frameworks and areas requiring more precise theories. Understanding field clustering enhances researchers' ability to formulate appropriate conceptual building blocks.
Corsini <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Present two instrumental case studies of maker projects that use digital fabrication to tackle COVID-19	Case study	The authors were able to highlight the parallels between the processes and results of frugal innovation and creators and identify many shared attributes between them. This research suggests that digital manufacturing helps amplify the work of the frugal innovator, both in its ability to develop frugal solutions and in its support of distributed maker networks.
Borchardt <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Analyze the factors that influence frugal innovation	Case study	The investigation found that ordinary capabilities remain stagnant in companies

	in micro and small MSEs at the base of the pyramid through the theoretical lens of dynamic capabilities.		with weak dynamic capabilities, and frugal innovation occurs sporadically, often driven by external agents. Maintaining ordinary capabilities in an overwhelming environment that overwhelms energy-poor individuals drains entrepreneurs and hampers their innovation ability. Structural poverty is an inhibitor of dynamic capabilities, creating a barrier to innovation.
Lange <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Explore how frugal innovation impacts inclusive business design	Case study	The research sheds light on how frugal innovation can enhance inclusive business design and vice versa. Drawing from African case studies, it was proposed that implementing frugal innovation through inclusive business approaches leads to varying levels of integration. The inclusive business integration ladder model's descriptive framework categorizes this integration. The study emphasizes knowledge transfer as a crucial prerequisite.

TABLE S4. CLUSTER 3 ARTICLES, WITH THEIR SYNTHESIS.

Author	Objective	Method	Results/Contributions
Iqbal <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Investigate the sustainable leadership-environmental performance mechanism based on upper echelon theory (UET).	Structural Equation Modeling	Frugal innovation partially mediated sustainable leadership in environmental performance.
Xuecheng and Iqbal (2022)	Examine the integrated relationships of business ties, political ties, sustainable leadership, and frugal innovation.	Structural Equation Modeling	The study found that managerial and commercial ties significantly impact frugal innovation, especially when combined with sustainable leadership. However, political ties did not positively impact frugal innovation, even after considering sustainable leadership in Pakistani SMEs.

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